

***Onthophagus*, fruits and diplopods relationship in Senegal**

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Abstract.— Observations on fruit feeding by *Onthophagus* in Senegal are presented. A direct relation between this type of feeding behaviour and the presence of diplopods in fruits is proposed. An annotated list of collected species is given.

Key words.— Scarabaeidae, Scarabaeinae, *Onthophagus*, frugivory, diplopods, ecology, ethology.

Interaction entre *Onthophagus*, fruits et diplopes au Sénégal

Résumé.— Les observations rapportées ici concernent la consommation de fruits par des *Onthophagus* au Sénégal. Une relation entre ce comportement alimentaire et la présence systématique de diplopes dans les fruits est évoquée. La liste des espèces récoltées est établie et commentée.

Mots clefs.— Scarabaeidae, Scarabaeinae, *Onthophagus*, frugivorie, diplopes, écologie, éthologie.

INTRODUCTION

The decision to write this note was made in Senegal. It was still only a project when Jean-Pierre Lumaret informed me that Gonzalo HALFFTER (2009) was preparing a synthesis on Scarabaeinae using vegetal matter and was looking for unpublished data to complete a chapter dealing with the African fauna. I therefore started to compile data on the observations made in 2008, which dealt mostly with *Onthophagus callosipennis* Boucomont, 1930, to be used by our eminent colleague. The work was ready to be published when François Génier and myself, during a new expedition to Senegal in 2009, were fortunate enough to make field observations of larva and teneral adults of *O. callosipennis* in their cells, completing previous observations. Observations were made during the rainy season from July 31 to August 3, 2008 by the author and completed on September 5-6, 2009 by François Génier and the author in the Forêt classée de Bakor (12°51'30"N 14°49'40"W) near Kolda, Senegal.

Observations made in 2008. This soudanian forest (Guinean forest-savanna mosaic (AT0707) Ecoregion)¹ is characterized by its numerous *Cordyla pinnata* (Lepr. ex A. Rich) Milne-Redh, ndimb in Wolof (Fig. 1). These trees produce fruits with a thick and nutritious pulp (16.7 g of glucids and 1.4 g of proteins for 100 g²) edible by humans. These fruits (Fig. 2), which were ripe, are equally appreciated by Pata monkeys (*Erythrocebus patas* (Schreber, 1774)³), which occur in the forest and make the fruit pulp available to insects. These monkeys rip the fruit open in two attached pieces, eat the pits and the surrounding pulp and through the rest of the fruit on the ground. Most of the time, these pieces return to their original position sealing the content and protecting it from desiccation and rain. A number of fruits are therefore found in a usually lightly shaded area and in different degraded states from freshly dropped to a more or less nutritious composted state. It should be pointed out that unless the

¹ <http://www.nationalgeographic.com/wildworld/terrestrial.html> (accessed march 2009)

² <http://www.i-dietetique.com/?action=table-composition-aliment&id=13989> (accessed march 2009)

³ <http://www.iucnredlist.org/details/8073> (accessed march 2009)

position allows it, rain does not accumulated inside the fruit and little fermentation takes place. Occasionally, fruits fall intact on the ground, naturally or due to disturbance by monkeys. As the peel is flexible but tough, it takes longer for the pulp to be accessible to insects. Nearly all of the fruits, except those that are fermented, sheltered diplopods (Fig. 3) and/or *Onthophagus* (Fig. 4). Diplopods, which seem to be the first entrants, systematically visit the inside of the freshest fruits, consume the pulp surface of and soil it with their excrements. All of the freshest fruits observed had been soiled before the arrival of the *Onthophagus*. It is suggested that Diplopods excrements play a role in pulp transformation into compost from its bacterial content, the phenomenon being accelerated by the *Onthophagus* mashing action. Some specimens were found buried beneath the fruit and the presence of pulp or litter could not be identified. The question being what attracted *Onthophagus* first: diplopods, diplopods excrement, fruit pulp or soiled fruit pulp by diplopods excrements? In order to answer that question, at least partially, two pitfall traps baited with fresh squished ndimb fruits and two traps baited with injured diplopods have been set in the same lightly shadowed areas but not under ndimb in order to avoid interference, for two days and two nights. The following species were collected:

1) Species collected in fruits remains on the ground.

Species	Number of specimen
<i>O. callosipennis</i>	56
<i>O. cupreus</i>	2
<i>O. (Furconthophagus) flaviclava</i>	139
«cf. <i>Amietina</i> » sp.	1

2) Species collected in pitfall traps baited with fresh, squished fruits.

Species	Number of specimen
<i>O. (Furconthophagus) flaviclava</i>	8

3) Species collected in pitfall traps baited with injured diplopods.

Species	Number of specimen
<i>Anachalcos aurescens</i>	9
<i>O. altidorsis</i>	4
<i>O. chrysoderus</i>	3
<i>O. flexicornis</i>	2
<i>O. imbellis</i>	8
<i>O. latigibber</i>	23
<i>O. maculatus</i>	6
<i>O. mocquerysi</i>	1
<i>O. quiiproquo</i>	1
<i>O. rougonorum</i>	7
<i>O. stehliki</i>	2
<i>O. trinominatus</i>	31
<i>O. tripartitus</i>	1
<i>O. vultuosus</i>	1
<i>O. (furconthophagus) flaviclava</i>	4

Observations made in 2009. In September, as the rainy season was well advanced,

only a few highly degraded fruits remains were present on the ground. The pulp had more or less turned into humus and specimens of *O. callosipennis* were still numerous. Of course the *Onthophagus* reproduction cycle state was more advanced and it allowed us to find brood cells (Fig. 7) in about 5 cm deep burrows under one of the fruit, larvae (Fig. 6) and even teneral adults (Fig. 8) of *O. callosipennis*. It was not possible to use fresh fruits as bait as the season was too late but four pitfall traps were baited with diplopods.

1) Species collected in fruit remains on the ground.

Species	Number of specimen
<i>O. callosipennis</i>	40

2) Species collected in pitfall traps baited with injured diplopods.

Species	Number of specimen
<i>Sisyphus sp.</i>	1
<i>Metacatharsius cf. tchadensis</i>	1
<i>O. flexicornis</i>	1
<i>O. latigibber</i>	41
<i>O. maculatus</i>	19
<i>O. mucronatus</i>	1
<i>O. quioproquo</i>	1
<i>O. rougonorum</i>	6
<i>O. sp. 1</i>	16
<i>O. sp. 2</i>	1
<i>O. trinominatus</i>	20
<i>O. vultuosus</i>	4

RESULTS

Onthophagus callosipennis Boucomont, 1930

This nocturnal species, which was considered rare, seems to prefer wooded areas. It is attracted to snake carrion (CAMBEFORT, 1984) but especially to rotting vegetation: *Nauclea latifolia* Sm. in Ivory Coast (CAMBEFORT, 1984; personal observation) and mushrooms in Ivory Coast and Senegal (MORETTO & GÉNIER, 2010). According to Cambefort (pers. comm.) « les fruits de *Nauclea* tombés sous l'arbre étaient "gâtés", rendus plus mous par cet état de semi-corruption, et les *Onthophagus* s'y enfonçaient (superficiellement) comme dans un excrément de texture ferme (cf. crottin de mouton), le tout en l'absence apparente de diplopodes. ». Despite the fact that this species belongs to a group that is partially necrophagous and frequently attracted to dead diplopods, none of the specimens has been collected using pitfall traps baited with such bait or in traps baited with fresh crushed fruits. The only three specimens collected in the Niokolo-Koba National Park (MORETTO & GÉNIER, 2009) were collected in pitfall traps baited with mushroom despite several traps baited with carrion in the same biotope. In Ivory Coast, this species has always been collected as singletons in mushrooms. The capture of numerous specimens (56 in 2008 and 40 in 2009) of *O. callosipennis* inside fruits of *Cordyla pinnata in situ* under the trees, leaves no more doubt about its dependence on plant material, most likely fruits, and support the hypothesis of an attraction by the peels contaminated by the diplopods. The discovery, under the fruits in 2009, of larvae in their cell supplied with humus from fruit pulp and presence of teneral adults

confirm this hypothesis and prove that the complete species life cycle depend on fruit pulp.

***Onthophagus cupreus* Harold, 1880**

This diurnal species, widespread in Sudanian and Guinean West African savannas, is at the boundary of its distribution and rare, represented by individuals of small size and very dark color, bronze or blue. It is attracted to traps baited with human excrement and I collected a specimen as it was landing at the foot of a fresh mushroom in Ivory Coast. Its biology is unknown. I have never collected specimens in traps baited with diplopods or small carrion.

Two females were found in their burrows under a fruit. One of these burrows was partly filled with fresh pulp (Fig. 5), but it is impossible to say if it was a chamber for reproduction or a food reserve. The few specimens obtained in traps baited with human feces were also females.

“cf. *Amietina*” sp.

This is likely a new species, currently under study, near *Amietina* Cambefort, 1981. Although only one specimen has been collected, the fact that it belongs to a new species, and perhaps even a new genus, and being from an African region where the Scarabaeinae dung beetle fauna is relatively well known, suggest that it could be a fruit specialist.

***Onthophagus (Furconthophagus) flaviclava* d’Orbigny, 1902**

This opportunistic diurnal species, mainly coprophagous, abundant in the Sudanian and Guinean savannas and dry forests is attracted to all bait types, particularly to human and baboons feces. Its attraction in number by the fruits *in situ* under the trees, however, is significant and supports the hypothesis of an attraction by the fruit remains contaminated by the Diplopods feces.

***Onthophagus imbellis* d’Orbigny, 1905**

***Onthophagus maculatus* (Fabricius, 1801)**

***Onthophagus latigibber* d’Orbigny, 1902**

***Onthophagus trinominatus* Goidanich, 1926**

***Onthophagus* sp. 1**

These five species are exclusively attracted by the dead of diplopods, which they depend on. The first two are diurnal and prefer sunny areas; the last three are nocturnal. *Onthophagus latigibber* and *O. trinominatus* favor shady places.

***Onthophagus altidorsis* d’Orbigny, 1905**

***Onthophagus chrysoderus* d’Orbigny, 1905**

***Onthophagus flexicornis* d’Orbigny, 1902**

***Onthophagus rougonorum* Cambefort, 1984**

***Onthophagus tripartitus* d’Orbigny, 1902**

***Onthophagus vultuosus* d’Orbigny, 1902**

These six nocturnal species are attracted to human feces baited dung traps but also very often to small carrion, including diplopods when they ceased to attract the species of the previous group. *O. altidorsis* is also attracted by carnivore feces (CAMBEFORT, 1984, KRELL & al., 2003, MORETTO & BORDAT, 2007).

Fig 1-5 : 1. *Cordyla pinnata* or ndimb, 2. Fruits and fruit remains of *Cordyla pinnata*. We can see (right side, middle) incisions made by monkeys teeth, 3. Diplopodes in fruit remain, 4. *Onthophagus callosipennis* in fruit remain, 5. *O. cupreus* tunnel containing ndimb pulp.

Fig. 6-8. *Onthophagus callosipennis* : 6. Larva, 7. Pupation cell, 8. Immature in pupation cell.

***Onthophagus mocquersyi* d'Orbigny, 1902**

***Onthophagus quiproquo* Moretto & Génier, 2010**

These two species, also nocturnal, are mainly attracted by small vertebrate carrion, including snakes and aging diplopods carrion, and are probably necrophagous.

***Anachalcos aurescens* Bates, 1888**

***Sisyphus* sp.**

***Metacatharsius cf. tchadensis* Balthasar, 1961**

***Onthophagus mucronatus* Thomson, 1858**

***Onthophagus stehliki* Balthasar, 1966**

These five species are coprophagous and are mainly attracted to excrement. The first three are nocturnal, the following two are diurnal.

Preferences for *Onthophagus* sp. 2 are unknown, but it belongs to a group of species frequently attracted to small vertebrate and aging diplopods carrions.

CONCLUSION

Onthophagus callosipennis is the only species that is attracted almost exclusively to more or less rotten plant material (fungi and in particular fruits), the remains of ndimb fruits soiled by diplopods in this case. The field observations show, as one might expect, that there is no correlation between species attracted to peels of ndimb fruits (*O. callosipennis*) and those, more abundant, attracted by the diplopods, most of which are regular or compulsory diplopods consumers. Living and non-injured diplopods in the peel are not attractive to species usually attracted by dead or wounded diplopods. Fresh ndimb fruits however, have proved unattractive. These results guide us towards an interaction between diplopods feces and pulp in the fruit peel, pulp making the feces attractive and usable by certain *Onthophagus*, at least as food source. The fact that a species is regularly attracted or favors decomposing plants, old dead iules or dead snakes, for example, does not imply that it uses these resources for its reproduction, but only suggest the hypothesis (CAMBEFORT, 1984). Finally, it should be kept in mind that if a species is attracted by a particular type of substance, that it is a consequence of its chemoreceptors being sensitive to volatile molecules that are associated and that this attraction derive from a need. For example, important amino acids essential for the maturation of reproductive organs during a feeding phase, then the constitution of food reserves of the larva in a nesting phase, needs and substances used are not necessarily the same for both phases (CAMBEFORT, 1984). In the case of *O. callosipennis*, the presence of adults in degraded ndimb fruit, larvae and teneral adults in their cell under the same fruit prove that this species accomplish its entire life cycle using fruits pulp.

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